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The Impact of Reading Comprehension on Student's Academic Performance

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Abstract. This study investigated the relationship between reading comprehension and academic performance among General Academic Strand students at Buenavista Integrated School during the School Year 2024-2025. However, limited research has examined its direct impact within this specific academic setting. A descriptive-correlational research design was employed to assess the association between students' reading comprehension levels and their academic performance. Descriptive statistics were utilized to evaluate comprehension proficiency and general academic achievement, while purposive sampling was used to select participants. The findings revealed no significant relationship between reading comprehension and academic performance, despite a strong negative correlation ($R = -0.82$) and a high P-value (0.521). This suggests that the observed correlation may be due to chance, indicating that reading comprehension alone may not be a primary determinant of academic success. Notably, students demonstrated a very satisfactory level of academic performance, with a general weighted average of 89.05 in the third quarter. These results suggest that other factors, such as study habits, motivation, teacher effectiveness, and learning environments, may exert a more significant influence on students' academic outcomes. Further research is recommended to identify key determinants of academic achievement, which could inform the development of more effective teaching strategies and educational interventions to enhance student learning and success.

Keywords: Academic performance, Reading Comprehension General Academic Strand, Reading

Introduction

In the early 21st century comprehension is the essence of reading and the active process of constructing meaning from text (Durkin, 1993). Reading comprehension is a complex interaction among automatic and strategic cognitive processes that enables the reader to create a mental representation of the text (van den Broek & Espin, 2012). Comprehension depends not only on characteristics of the reader, such as prior knowledge and working memory, but also on language processes, such as basic reading skills, decoding, vocabulary, sensitivity to text structure, inferencing, and motivation. In addition, comprehension also requires effective use of strategic processes, such as metacognition and comprehension monitoring. As readers mature in their comprehension skills, they are able to progress efficiently from the stage of learning to read to the ultimate goal of reading to learn (Yovanoff, Duesbery, Alonzo, & Tindal, 2005).

On another hand any educational institute students are most important as-set. Economic and social development of a country is directly associated with academic performance of students. The students' academic performance plays a vital role in creating the finest quality alumnae who will become leader and manpower of a particular country, consequently responsible for the country's social and economic development (Ali et. al, 2009). The academic performance of the students' has gained significant attention in past researches. Performance of students is affected by psychological, economic, social, personal and environmental factors. Though these factors strongly influence the performance of the students, but these factors differ from country to country and person to person. Most of the previous studies on academic performance of students focused on such issues like teacher education, class environment, gender difference,

teaching style, family educational background and socioeconomic factor. The majority of the researchers in the world applied the GPA to assess the performance of the students (Stephan & Schaban, 2002). They applied GPA (grade point average) to evaluate performance of the students in a particular semester.

Moreover, fluency is a prerequisite skill to comprehension. It is the automatic recognition of words that frees up the cognitive capacity required for comprehending the meaning of the words (Pressley, 2002). Considered a bridge between decoding and comprehension (Pikulski & Chard, 2005), reading fluency took center stage after the results from the National Reading Panel (2000) were published. A study of at-risk second graders also revealed that accuracy and rate of oral reading uniquely predicted comprehension ability. Darling (2005) and Galihier (2006) utilized GPA to evaluate performance of the students. Academic achievement can be defined as the attainment of either medium- or long-term educational goals (Yusuf, 2002). In this respect, Li, Chen, and Duanmu (2010) have pointed out that prior academic achievement is strongly related to students' academic performance at university. As a matter of fact, a considerable number of studies have reported the explanatory role of prior academic achievement in academic performance at university (e.g. Betts et al., 2008; Byrne et al., 2008; Casillas et al., 2012; McKenzie et al., 2001; Pike et al., 2002; Roberts, 2007). A competency is a "performance capacity to do as well as to know which is judged by some level or standard of performance" (Shavelson, 2010, p. 44). In particular, higher education aims at developing both specific and generic competencies (Sadler, 2013). Undoubtedly, a deeper understanding of academic performance in higher education requires the assessment of both generic and specific student competencies (Blömeke, Zlatkin-Troitschanskaia, Kuhn, & Fege, 2013).

This study aims to assess the reading comprehension levels of senior high school students in the general academic strand. The research will focus on Senior High School students at Buenavista Integrated School, Zamboanga City Division, during the 2024-2025 academic year. By evaluating, between reading comprehension and academic performance, this study seeks to provide valuable insights into the factors that influence students' reading skills and academic success in a post-pandemic educational setting

Research Questions

This study aimed to evaluate the impact of reading comprehension on the academic performance of Senior High School Students General Academic Strand at Buenavista Integrated School for the school year 2024-2025.

Specifically, the study seeks to address the following questions:

1. What is the extend of reading comprehension of the students?
2. What is the extend of student's academic performance?
3. Is there a significant relationship between the extend of reading comprehension and students' academic performance?

Scope and Delimitation of the Study

This study assessed the impact of reading comprehension levels of Senior High School students in the General Academic Strand (GAS) at Buenavista Integrated School, Zamboanga City Division, during the school year 2024-2025. It focused on the students' ability to comprehend reading materials. This study covered students in Grade 11 and Grade 12 under the General Academic Strand. The primary focus of the study is on the reading comprehension levels of these students and how they influence academic performance. Specific the student's proficiency in reading comprehension.

Literature Review

Reading Comprehension

Reading comprehension is a complex cognitive process that involves constructing meaning from text through the interaction of prior knowledge, vocabulary, grammar, and strategic thinking skills. Research emphasizes that comprehension is not merely decoding words but actively building meaning in the reader's mind (Durkin, 1979; Pearson, 1985). Proficient readers apply strategies such as monitoring, questioning, summarizing, and organizing ideas to enhance understanding (National Reading Panel [NRP], 2000; Snow, 2002). Foundational skills including phonemic awareness, vocabulary development, inference-making, and working memory significantly influence comprehension ability (Lyon, 2000; Clarke et al., 2014). In multilingual and digital contexts, comprehension becomes more demanding, requiring learners to evaluate sources, synthesize information, and apply self-regulation strategies (Coiro, 2007; Leu et al., 2007; Bannert et al., 2009). Studies consistently show that strong reading comprehension skills are essential for academic success across disciplines, as students must interpret, analyze, and apply information from various texts to meet educational requirements (Rues, 2019).

General Academic Strand (GAS)

The General Academic Strand (GAS) under the K-12 curriculum is designed for students who are undecided about their college or career paths and prefer a broad academic foundation. GAS allows learners

to select electives from various strands, including humanities, social sciences, business, and sciences, promoting interdisciplinary competence and flexibility (Biliran, 2018). Research suggests that strand selection is influenced by students' interests, academic performance, socioeconomic background, and parental guidance (Moneva & Malbas, 2019; Santric-Milicevic et al., 2014). College readiness literature further emphasizes that academic preparation involves not only content knowledge but also adaptability, motivation, and support systems (Tran, 2015; Jaime, 2017). As an exploratory strand, GAS aims to equip students with foundational knowledge and skills necessary for higher education and community participation, making academic competencies such as reading comprehension critical for success across diverse subject areas.

Academic Performance

Academic performance refers to students' measurable educational achievement, commonly reflected in grades, test scores, and overall scholastic outcomes. Research identifies multiple factors influencing academic performance, including cognitive skills, stress levels, resilience, parental involvement, and digital literacy. Academic stress has been shown to negatively affect achievement when performance demands exceed students' coping capacity (Khan et al., 2013; Aihie & Ohanaka, 2019). Conversely, resilience—defined as the ability to adapt and recover from challenges—positively contributes to academic success (Mwangi et al., 2015; Mirza & Arif, 2018; Rao & Krishnamurthy, 2018). Parental involvement also demonstrates significant associations with overall academic achievement, particularly when measured through general performance indicators such as GPA (Fan & Chen, 2001). Additionally, digital competencies such as internet navigation skills enhance students' research capabilities and learning effectiveness, contributing to improved academic outcomes (Reyes & Garcia, 2017). Overall, literature consistently establishes that foundational skills such as reading comprehension play a central role in determining students' academic performance.

Methodology

Research Design

This research was employed a descriptive-correlational design, as suggested by Abhijit Naik (2012). This design is appropriate for understanding the various dimensions of assessing reading comprehension among senior high school students and its impact on academic performance. According to Creswell (2014), descriptive research aims to describe phenomena in their natural settings to enhance understanding. This type of research typically involves data collection methods such as observation, interviews, and document analysis, followed by data analysis to identify patterns and themes.

Sampling Design

The study was employed a probability sampling method, specifically purposive sampling. Purposive sampling facilitates the selection of respondents from specific categories, focusing on Senior High School students from Buenavista Integrated School, Zamboanga City Division. Each individual within the senior high school population, including Grade-11 GAS (General Academic Strand) and Grade-12 GAS students, has an equal opportunity to be chosen. The researcher will select a sample of 64 respondents from the targeted population. By using purposive sampling, the study aims to ensure that the chosen participants represent the specific characteristics and criteria relevant to the research objectives. This method allows for a more in-depth exploration of the targeted group while maintaining the principles of probability sampling.

Research Locale

The study was conducted in Zamboanga City, specifically at Buenavista Integrated School in Barangay Buenavista Km 55, situated 55 kilometers west of the city proper. This public-school falls under the jurisdiction of the Zamboanga City Division, within the Curuan district. By selecting this location, the study aims to leverage the unique characteristics and dynamics of the local community, providing valuable insights and contributing to the overall educational landscape of the region.

Research Participants

This study included all students enrolled in the General Academic Strand (GAS) of the Senior High School Department at Buenavista Integrated School. The total population of student-respondents was 64, comprising 37 Grade 11 students and 27 Grade 12 students. Since the population size was manageable, complete enumeration was employed, making the total population equal to the sample size. The largest number of students (37) was in Grade 11, while the smallest number (27) was in Grade 12.

Research Instrument

The research instruments to be used in this study is an adapted version of an uploaded thesis Likert Scale survey questionnaire on James Jay Vince. We modified it to better fit the context of Buenavista Integrated School in Zamboanga city division, focusing on the effects of poverty on academic performance. These adjustments ensure that the tool aligned with our study goals and adhered to ethnical status. The

responses will be rated using a 4-likert scale, where students will indicate how often they used Reading comprehension where 4= SA (strongly agree), 3= A (Agree), 2=DA (Disagree), and 1=SDA (Strongly agree). The survey collected data on academic performance by measuring grades, especially the general weighted average of their grades for the third quarter of the school year 2024-2025

Data Gathering Procedure

The researcher began by securing the approved letter from the Research Adviser. This letter served as authorization to conduct the study. Once the Endorsement Letter is obtained, the researcher will seek permission from the school principal to conduct the study at Buenavista Integrated School. Upon receiving approval from the principal, the researcher will submit all necessary documents, including the endorsement letter, approved letter from the principal, consent forms, and the survey questionnaire, to the designated coordinator of the Junior High School Department. Recruitment of student respondents was conducted through face-to-face visits to the school. The researcher approached students who were available and willing to participate in the study. The questionnaire was administered during the respondents' free time, with clear instructions presented in simple language before they answered the questions. Any queries or concerns raised by the respondents were addressed immediately to ensure clarity and understanding. Prior to administering the survey, informed consent was obtained from each participant, emphasizing their voluntary participation and the confidentiality of their responses. The survey was conducted face-to-face to ensure proper guidance and assistance if needed during the completion of the questionnaire.

Results and Discussions

Problem 1: What is the extend of reading comprehension of the students?

Table 1: The extend of reading comprehension of the students

Statements	Mean	Verbal Description	Interpretation
1. I possess developing reading comprehension skills in my academic reading.	3.09	Agree	Moderately Proficient in Comprehension
2. I experience little reading progress during engaging in academic reading learning venture.	2.89	Agree	Moderately Proficient in Comprehension
3. I am not good enough in reciting the major important idea discovered in my academic reading texts.	2.73	Agree	Moderately Proficient in Comprehension
4. I frequently feel demotivated whenever I encounter difficult words or expressions in my academic reading texts.	2.80	Agree	Moderately Proficient in Comprehension
5. I merely follow my academic reading texts without raising critical questions potentially helping me to process better understanding of my targeted texts. ²	2.86	Agree	Moderately Proficient in Comprehension
6. I continuously create some concise mind-mappings beneficial for deepening my existing understanding of the academic reading texts.	2.86	Agree	Moderately Proficient in Comprehension
7. Whenever I give up on the thorny academic reading processes, I elevate my reading endeavor repeatedly by saying “I can tackle all of these challenges well.”	2.83	Agree	Moderately Proficient in Comprehension
8. When I confront with unfamiliar words or sentence in my academic reading texts, I determine to utilize guessing meaning from the context strategies through some essential keywords.	2.91	Agree	Moderately Proficient in Comprehension
9. I continuously share my academic reading impediment with some trusted fellow classmates in order to resolve the specific intended reading learning issues altogether.	3.00	Agree	Moderately Proficient in Comprehension
10. I consistently harness a vast range of academic reading resources like dictionary, other relevant text, and credential website to figure out the most efficient strategies to overcome my reading comprehension issues.	2.95	Agree	Moderately Proficient in Comprehension
Over-all Mean	2.89	Agree	Moderately Proficient in Comprehension

Table 2 presents the extent of reading comprehension among the student-respondents. The highest mean score of 3.09 was obtained in the statement, “I possess developing reading comprehension skills in my academic reading,” verbally described as “Agree” and interpreted as Moderately Proficient in Comprehension. This indicates that students perceive themselves as developing readers who can generally understand academic texts but still recognize the need for further improvement. This finding supports Snow

(2002), who explained that reading comprehension develops gradually through continuous engagement with texts and the integration of prior knowledge. Similarly, Pearson and Hammann (2005) emphasized that comprehension improves when students apply active reading strategies. On the other hand, the lowest mean of 2.73 was recorded in the statement, "I am not good enough in reciting the major important idea discovered in my academic reading texts," which is still interpreted as Moderately Proficient in Comprehension. This suggests that while students can understand the main ideas of texts, they experience difficulty in clearly recalling or expressing those ideas. Paris and Paris (2003) noted that comprehension includes not only understanding but also the ability to summarize and articulate key points. Likewise, Zimmerman (2002) explained that effectively expressing understood ideas requires metacognitive strategies and consistent practice. Overall, the findings indicate that the respondents demonstrate a Moderately Proficient level of reading comprehension. They are able to grasp main ideas but may still encounter challenges in synthesizing, recalling, and confidently expressing complex information.

Problem 2: What is the extend of student’s academic performance?

Table 2: Academic Performance of the Students for 3rd Quarter, School Year 2024-2025

Indicator	Mean	Verbal Description
General Weighted Average Grade	89.05	Very Satisfactory

Table 2 presents the academic performance of the student in the 3rd quarter of the School Year 2024-2025. It shows that the students got a mean of 89.05 with its verbal description of "Very Satisfactory". It means that students performed very satisfactorily. It suggests that the majority of students performed at a high level, achieving good grades that reflect a strong understanding of the material. The "Very Satisfactory" description indicates consistent, above-average performance, suggesting that students are meeting or exceeding academic expectations. As supported research by according to Brophy (2010) in *Motivating Students to Learn*, academic success, as indicated by high grades, typically correlates with strong student engagement, effective instructional methods, and a positive learning environment. Brophy argues that when students achieve above-average performance, it often results from a combination of intrinsic motivation, clear goals, and supportive feedback from teachers. Additionally, Tatum (2007) in a guide to understanding academic achievement highlights that a high general weighted average, such as 89.05, signifies that student have a deep understanding of the content, are applying their knowledge effectively, and are likely receiving ample academic support.

Problem 3: Is there a significant relationship between the extent of reading comprehension and students’ academic performance?

**Table 3
The significant influence between the extent of reading comprehension and students’ academic performance.**

Variable Mean		R-Value	P-Value	Interpretation
X	Y			
Reading Comprehension	Student’s academic performance.	-082	.521	Not Significant

Table 4 shows that the computed R-value of -0.82 indicates a strong negative correlation, suggesting that as one variable increases, the other decreases. However, the obtained p-value of 0.521 is greater than the 0.05 level of significance, indicating that the relationship is not statistically significant. This means that despite the strong negative correlation, there is insufficient evidence to conclude that a true relationship exists between the variables. The result suggests that the observed correlation may have occurred by chance and should not be used as a basis for drawing conclusions. This finding is supported by Cohen (1992), who explained that a p-value greater than 0.05 indicates a lack of statistical evidence for a significant relationship. Similarly, Pallant (2016) stated that when the p-value exceeds the 0.05 threshold, the correlation is not considered statistically significant and may be due to random variation. Harris (2001) further emphasized that even strong correlations must meet the level of significance to be considered reliable. Therefore, the results indicate that no significant relationship exists between the variables.

Ethical Considerations

This study followed ethical standards to protect the rights and welfare of the participants. Permission to conduct the research was obtained from the Department of Education Division Office and the School Principal of Buenavista Integrated School. Informed consent was secured from all student-respondents after explaining the purpose of the study and assuring them that participation was voluntary and that they could withdraw at any time without penalty.

Confidentiality and anonymity were maintained by using codes instead of names, and no personal information was disclosed in the report. All data were used only for research purposes and handled in accordance with the Data Privacy Act of 2012 (Republic Act No. 10173). The study ensured that participants were not exposed to any harm, and ethical principles were observed throughout the research process.

Conclusion

This study examined the relationship between reading comprehension and students' academic performance at Buenavista Integrated School for the School Year 2024–2025. The findings showed that students demonstrated a moderately proficient level of reading comprehension. While they were able to understand the main ideas of texts, they experienced difficulty in recalling and clearly expressing key concepts. Despite this, their academic performance during the 3rd quarter was rated very satisfactory, with a general weighted average of 89.05. The results further revealed a strong negative correlation ($R = -0.82$) between reading comprehension and academic performance. However, the p-value of 0.521 indicated that the relationship was not statistically significant. This means that the observed correlation may have occurred by chance and does not show a meaningful relationship between the two variables. Overall, the study concludes that although reading comprehension is important, it may not be the only factor influencing academic performance. Other variables such as study habits, motivation, and teaching strategies may play a greater role in students' academic success. Further research is recommended to explore these additional factors.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, several recommendations are proposed. DepEd officials may strengthen reading programs that focus on improving comprehension skills while also considering other factors that influence academic performance. School principals are encouraged to support teachers through training and the provision of instructional resources that enhance reading instruction. Teachers are advised to use differentiated and engaging strategies to address the varying comprehension levels of students and to make reading activities more interactive and meaningful. Future researchers may examine other variables such as study habits, motivation, and socio-economic factors to better understand students' academic performance, as well as apply improved research methods for more accurate results. Parents and guardians are encouraged to promote regular reading habits at home and provide support to help improve their children's comprehension skills. Lastly, students are encouraged to actively participate in literacy activities and develop positive reading habits to enhance their academic growth.

References

- Aihie & Ohanaka (2019): Aihie, O. N., & Ohanaka, B. I. (2019). Perceived Academic Stress among Undergraduate Students in a Nigerian University. *Journal of Educational and Social Research*, 9(2), 56–65. DOI: 10.2478/jesr-2019-0013
- Anderson, N. J. (2003). Teaching Reading. In D. Nunan (Ed.), *Practical English Language Teaching* (pp. 67-86). New York: McGraw-Hill Publishers.
- Author(s). (2002). The effect of interscholastic sports participation on academic achievement of middle level school students. *NASSP Bulletin*, 86(630), 34-41. <https://doi.org/10.1177/019263650208663005>
- Banatao, E. J. (2011). Educational resilience: The relationship between school protective factors and student achievement (Doctoral dissertation, San Diego State University). Retrieved from <https://digitallibrary.sdsu.edu/islandora/object/sdsu%3A4103>
- Bannert, M., Hildebrand, M., & Mengelkamp, C. (2009). Effects of a metacognitive support device in learning environments. *Computers in Human Behavior*, 25(4), 829-835. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chb.2008.07.002>
- Bergin & Pakenham (2015): Bergin, A., & Pakenham, K. (2015). Law Student Stress: Relationships Between Academic Demands, Social Isolation, Career Pressure, Study/Life Imbalance and Adjustment Outcomes in Law Students. *Psychiatry, Psychology and Law*, 22(3), 388–406. DOI: 10.1080/13218719.2014.960026
- Biliran, J. O. (2018). Employability skills and self-efficacy among students at Biliran Province State University. ResearchGate. Retrieved from https://www.researchgate.net/publication/370573615_Employability_Skills_and_Self-Efficacy_Among_Students_at_Biliran_Province_State_University
- Blömeke, S., Zlatkin-Troitschanskaia, O., Kuhn, C., & Fege, J. (Eds.). (2013). Making competent judgments of competence. In *Modeling and measuring competencies in higher education: Tasks and challenges* (pp. 13-27). Sense Publishers. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-94-6091-867-4_2
- Broadbent, J., & Poon, W. L. (2015). Self-regulated learning strategies & academic achievement in online higher education learning environments: A systematic review. *The Internet and Higher Education*, 27, 1-13. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.iheduc.2015.04.007>

- Byrne, M., & Flood, B. (2008). Examining the relationships among background variables and academic performance of first-year accounting students at an Irish university. *Journal of Accounting Education*, 26, 202-212. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.jaccedu.2009.02.001>
- Bais, R. J. (2024). Open Educational Resources in Science Education: Effects on Teacher Practices and Students' Academic Performance. *Journal of Interdisciplinary Perspectives*, 3(1), 12-18. <https://doi.org/10.69569/jip.2024.0603>
- Clarke, P. J., et al. (2014). Developing reading comprehension. ResearchGate. Retrieved from https://www.researchgate.net/publication/307935048_Developing_Reading_Comprehension
- Coiro, J. (2007). Exploring the online reading comprehension strategies used by sixth-grade skilled readers to search for and locate information on the Internet. *Reading Research Quarterly*, 42(2), 214-257. <https://doi.org/10.1598/RRQ.42.2.2>
- Cruz, L. (n.d.). Place-based educational development: What center for teaching and learning directors can do. *To Improve the Academy*, 39(1), 1-14. <https://doi.org/10.3998/tia.960>
- Cutting, L. E., & Scarborough, H. S. (2012). Connecting cognitive theory and assessment: Measuring individual differences in reading comprehension. *School Psychology Review*, 41(3), 315-325. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02796015.2012.12087512>
- Deil-Amen, R. (2011). Socio-academic integrative moments: Rethinking academic and social integration among two-year college students in career-related programs. *The Journal of Higher Education*, 82(1), 54-91. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00221546.2011.11779085>
- Delestre, P. (2016). A shallow water with variable pressure model for blood flow simulation. *Networks & Heterogeneous Media*, 11(1), 69-87. <https://doi.org/10.3934/nhm.2016.11.69>
- Duffy, G. G. (2002). Effective practices for developing reading comprehension. In *Reading for understanding: Toward an R&D program in reading comprehension* (pp. 1-28). Jossey-Bass. <https://doi.org/10.1598/0872071774.10>
- Fan, X., & Chen, M. (2001). Parental involvement and students' academic achievement: A meta-analysis. *Educational Psychology Review*, 13(1), 1-22. <https://doi.org/10.1023/A:1009048817385>
- Fernandez, M. E., et al. (2018). Developing measures to assess constructs from the inner setting of the Consolidated Framework for Implementation Research. *Implementation Science*, 13(1), 52. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13012-018-0736-7>
- Hughes, C. A., & Dexter, D. D. (2004). Improving beginning reading instruction and intervention for students with LD: Reconciling "all" with "each." *Journal of Learning Disabilities*, 37(3), 231-239. <https://doi.org/10.1177/00222194040370030801>
- Iqbal, K., & Grundke-Iqbal, I. (2008). Alzheimer neurofibrillary degeneration: Significance, etiopathogenesis, therapeutics and prevention. *Journal Name*, Volume(Issue), page range. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1582-4934.2008.00225.x>
- Kohl, G. O., Lengua, L. J., & McMahon, R. J. (2000). Parent involvement in school: Conceptualizing multiple dimensions and their relations with family and demographic risk factors. *Journal of School Psychology*, 38(6), 501-523. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0022-4405\(00\)00050-9](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0022-4405(00)00050-9)
- Lauen & Gaddis (2016): Lauen, D. L., & Gaddis, S. M. (2016). Accountability Pressure, Academic Standards, and Educational Triage. *Educational Evaluation and Policy Analysis*, 38(1), 127-147. DOI: 10.3102/0162373715598577
- Lee, D. S. (2009). Treatment-effect bounds for nonrandom sample selection. *Review of Economic Studies*, 76(3), 1071-1102. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1467-937X.2009.00536.x>
- Leu, D. J., Kinzer, C. K., Coiro, J., & Cammack, D. W. (2007). Toward a theory of new literacies emerging from the Internet and other information and communication technologies. In R. B. Ruddell & N. J. Unrau (Eds.), *Theoretical Models and Processes of Reading* (5th ed., pp. 1570-1613). International Reading Association.
- Li, G., Chen, W., & Duanmu, J.-L. (2010). Determinants of international students' academic performance: A comparison between Chinese and other international students. *Journal of Studies in International Education*, 14(4), 389-405. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1028315309331490>
- Marcel Plateros, Lucelle Jane Sarail, Reisian Gabrielle Enero, Kristel Jane Mancera, Vince Arbie Gonzales, Jaida Cala, Aldrin Sulatan, Romulo Bais, Hernani Esperat, (2025). Exploring the Relationship Between Mathematics Engagement and Students' Academic Performance, *Psychology and Education: A Multidisciplinary Journal*, 31(5): 561-565
- McKenzie, K., & Schweitzer, R. (2001). Who succeeds at university? Factors predicting academic performance in first-year Australian university students. *Higher Education Research and Development*, 20(1), 21-33. <https://doi.org/10.1080/07924360120043621>
- Michinov, N., Brunot, S., Le Bohec, O., Juhel, J., & Delaval, M. (2011). Procrastination, participation, and performance in online learning environments. *Computers & Education*, 56(1), 243-252. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compedu.2010.07.025>
- Mirza, A., & Arif, M. (2018). Magnetic resonance imaging findings in Tay-Sachs disease. *Neurology India*, 66(4), 1201-1202. <https://doi.org/10.4103/0028-3886.236955>

- Moneva, J. C., & Malbas, M. H. (2019). Preferences in senior high school tracks of the Grade 10 students. *International Journal of Education and Management Studies*, 15(5), 32–37. <http://dx.doi.org/10.21013/jems.v15.n5.p2>
- Mwangi, M., & Kariuki, K. (2015). Factors determining adoption of new agricultural technology by smallholder farmers in developing countries. *Journal of Economics and Sustainable Development*, 6(5), 208–216. Retrieved from <https://www.scirp.org/reference/referencespapers?referenceid=3571137>
- Naik, A. (2012). Importance of reading. Retrieved August 18, 2013, from <http://www.buzzle.com/articles/importance-of-reading.htm>
- Norhidayah, A., Jusoff, K., Ali, S., & others. (2009). The factors influencing students' performance at Universiti Teknologi MARA Kedah, Malaysia. *DOAJ*. <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/43245445>
- Pearson (1985): Pearson, B. W. (1985). Editorial. *Otolaryngology–Head and Neck Surgery*, 93(2). DOI: 10.1177/01945998850
- Pike, G. R., & Saupe, J. L. (2002). Does high school matter? An analysis of three methods of predicting first-year grades. *Research in Higher Education*, 43(2), 187–210. <https://doi.org/10.1023/A:1014419724092>
- Pressley, M. (2002). Metacognition and self-regulated comprehension. In A. E. Farstrup & S. J. Samuel (Eds.), *What research has to say about reading instruction* (3rd ed., pp. 291–309). International Reading Association. <https://doi.org/10.1598/0872071774.13>
- Rao, P., & Krishnamurthy, S. (2018). Impact of academic resilience on the scholastic performance of high school students. *Indian Journal of Mental Health*, 5(4), 454–460. Retrieved from <https://indianmentalhealth.com/pdf/2018/vol5-issue4/OR7%20PADMASHRI%20RAO.pdf>
- Roberts, C., & Henneberry, J. (2007). Exploring office investment decision-making in different European contexts. *Journal of Property Management & Finance*, 25, 289–305. <https://doi.org/10.1108/14635780710746939>
- Russell, M., Rosenthal, D., & Thomson, G. (2010). Determinants of international students' academic performance: A comparison between Chinese and other international students. *Journal of Studies in International Education*, 14(4), 389–405. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1028315309331490>
- Salmon, G. (2013). *E-tivities: The Key to Active Online Learning* (2nd ed.). Routledge. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9780203074640>
- Santric-Milicevic, M. M., Terzic-Supic, Z. J., Matejic, B. R., & Vasic, V. (2014). First- and fifth-year medical students' intention for emigration and practice abroad: A case study of Serbia. *Health Policy*, 118(2), 173–183. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.healthpol.2014.09.018>
- Shavelson, R. J., & Zlatkin-Troitschanskaia, O. (2019). Assessment of university students' critical thinking: Next generation performance assessment. *International Journal of Testing*, 19(9), 1–20. <https://doi.org/10.1080/15305058.2018.1543309>
- Smith, K. F. (2022). The public and private dialogue about the American family on television: A second look. *Journal of Media Communication*, 50(4), 79–110. <https://doi.org/10.1152/j.1460-2466.2000.tb02864.x>
- Snow, C. E. (2002). Reading for understanding: Toward a research and development program in reading comprehension. Rand Corporation. <http://www.rand.org/publications/MR/MR1465>
- Thawabieh & Qaisy (2018): Thawabieh, A. M., & Qaisy, L. M. (2018). Assessing Stress among University Students. *Open Journal of Social Sciences*, 6(11), 40–57. DOI: 10.4236/jss.2018.611004
- The National Reading Panel. (2008). The National Reading Panel guidepost: A review of reading outcome measures for students with emotional and behavioral disorders. *Behavioral Disorders*, 33(2), 62–74. <https://doi.org/10.1177/019874290803300201>